

The Effect of Crosscheck Approach on Oral Recitation Skills of Grade One Pupils in the Virtual Classroom

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Abstract. This study employed a quasi-experimental research design, specifically a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. The non-equivalent design was chosen due to the researcher's access to only one experimental group. The decision to use this design was influenced by the intact nature of the learner groups involved in the study. Conducted at Lt. C. Villafuerte Sr. Elementary School, the study included 68 grade one pupils, with 35 in section A constituting the control group and 33 in section B as the experimental group. Both sections were heterogeneous, ensuring comparable performance ranges among learners. Non-random assignment of subjects was employed, involving all learners from sections A and B as study participants. Virtual modality was utilized for classroom instruction, and both pre- and post-performance tests, consisting of a 25-item test administered with rubrics, were conducted. The pretest assessed pupils' decoding skills before treatment implementation, while the posttest evaluated treatment effects. Additionally, decoding skills of grade one pupils were assessed using a continuum based on the DepEd rating system.

KEY WORDS

1. crosscheck approach 2. decoding skills 3. heterogeneous

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1. Introduction

Virtual classroom is a digital learning environment that allows teachers to connect online in real time. It means an online system that permits students and teachers to communicate and collaborate. Online learning environments can offer learners opportunities for flexibility, interaction and collaboration (Wright, 2013). With the significant growth of e-learning, teachers and students explore new ways of building knowledge and improving teaching and learning capabilities beyond the four walls of the classroom. Despite our current situation, the researcher wants to make sure that the learning capabilities of our pupils will not be at stake.

Using cross check approach would be very helpful. Cross Checking is an approach for reading when learners do not know a word in the sentence. It is when the pupil thinks about what the sentence implies and imagines at the sounds in the word to help with decoding the word. They intend to make sure the sentence makes sense. Many struggling readers are taught to just "sound it out." For this cause, they often baffle phonics with reading (Cadwell 2019). Reading is more than simply sounding out words. Students need to learn that pronouncing words is only one part of reading to understand the author's meaning. With this strategy, the teacher

$O_1 \quad x \quad O_2$

$O_3 \quad x \quad O_4$

Where:

O_1 - Pretest of the experimental group

O_2 - Posttest of the experimental group

O_3 - Pretest of the controlled group

O_4 - Posttest of the controlled group

--- - Non-random assignment of subjects

X - Treatment applied in the experimental group

writes a sentence that contains one word covered up. The teacher then asks the students to fill the missing word. In order to provide this word, students “cross-check phonics clues with context clues in the sentence” (Jennings, 2014). In relation to education, teaching and learning in the class was demanded to be innovative and creative. In this case in English lessons especially reading skills are very low mastered by the students today. No doubt that today’s technology advances rapidly, but it is still lacking in improving students’ reading skills. Reading has the considerable role in the language teaching to strengthen the skills which are acquired by the students in listening, speaking, and writing (Maxom, 2009: 139). Reading skill affects the other skills learning process. Virtual classrooms and modular learning, as alternate technology-driven learning methods, have been escalating

at a rational time. In recent times, virtual classrooms have been particularly in use by all sectors, including primary and higher education learning. The growing acceptance of social and microlearning strategies, fostered by general social media platforms like YouTube, Zoom and google classroom, have added to the increasing acceptance of virtual modes of learning. It is expected that the predominant use of virtual classrooms would increase. In the Philippines, particularly in the division of Davao City, teachers encounter problem in the classroom when learners do not participate in class recitation particularly during pandemic time when classes are held online. This prompt the research to explore the crosscheck approach to validate if those learners who responds online during virtual classes are really themselves. Hence, this study.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study makes use of the quasi-experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good

design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

Distribution of Respondents

	Subjects	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	33
2	Section B	35
	Total	68

2.2. *Research Respondents*—This study was conducted in Lt. C. Villafuerte Sr. Elementary School. The subjects of this study will be the 68 grade one pupils – 33 are from section A which was the controlled group and 35 are from section B which was the experimental

group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. *Research Instrument*—This study will utilized the researcher-made pretest and posttest which will be the tool to measure the decoding proficiency of the grade one learners. Moreover, the researcher utilized topics which coverage is taken from the learning competencies of the grade one learners. The test questions were checked and validated by experts. The pretest and posttest are designed to measure the oral recitation skills of the grade one learners. The pretest and posttest consist of a 25 –item

test will eventually determine the oral recitation skills of the research subjects using rubrics. The subjects took the test twice (pretest and posttest). The pretest was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful to assess the oral recitation skills of the learners. On the hand, posttest was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the oral recitation skills of the grade one learners, the following variety was used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking for permission were sent to Reynante A. Solitario, CESO VI, the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Davao City and to the School Principal of Lt. C. Villafuerte Sr. Elementary School. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent and principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that

this study be conducted in Lt. C. Villafuerte Sr. Elementary School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher administered pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment by crosschecking the oral recitation performance of the learners in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made an analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the oral recitation skills of the

subjects from the controlled and experimental groups in the pretest and posttest. T-test for uncorrelated samples was used to test the significance of difference between the pretest and

Summary of Student Performance Levels

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

posttest mean scores in the experimental and on the oral recitation skills of the grade one n groups. Eta square was used to measure the learners. the magnitude of the effect of crosscheck approach

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 shows the pre-test scores of the grade one pupils. The controlled group got the mean of 38.65 or Developing while the experimental group got the mean of 38.80 or Developing. This means that student at this level possesses the minimum skills in oral recitation skills, but needs follow up and guidance in performing their tasks.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	25	38.65	77.30	Developing
Experimental Group	25	38.80	77.60	Developing

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test that the rating of the experimental group is slightly a higher over the controlled group although both belongs Developing level and we can consider that the lead is not significant. This finding is in line with the idea of Wrigth (2018) said that Virtual classroom is a digital learning environment that allows teachers to connect online in real time. It means an online system that permits students and teachers to communicate and collaborate. Online learning environments can offer learners opportunities for flexibility, interaction and collaboration (Wright, 2013). With the significant growth of e-learning, teachers and students explore new ways of building knowledge and improving teaching and learning capabilities beyond the four walls of the classroom. Despite our current situation, the researcher wants to make sure that the learning capabilities of our pupils will not be at stake. Using cross check approach would be very helpful. Cross Checking is an approach for reading when learners do not know a word in the sentence. It is when the pupil thinks about what the sentence implies and imagines at the sounds in the word to help with decoding the word. They intend to make sure the sentence makes sense. Numerous struggling readers are taught to just “sound it out.” For this cause, they often baffle phonics with reading (Cadwell 2019). Post-Test Score of Pupils Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade one pupils. The controlled group got the mean of 33.79 or Approaching while the experimental group gained the mean of 44.25 or Approaching. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 12.92 from a mean rating of 30.40 to 44.25. This means that students in the controlled group at this level has developed oral recitation skills but, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers. On the other hand, students in the experimental group at this level has devel-

oped the fundamental knowledge and skills and independently through authentic performance core understandings and, and can transfer them tasks.

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group	50	43.75	87.50	Approaching Proficiency
Experimental Group	48	45.30	90.60	Proficient

This finding is congruent to the idea of Campos (2017) who cited that formative assessment using oral recitation can provide valuable information pupils need. As stated by Campos and O’Hern, “Cross checking from assessments can be used to help pupils with goal setting. This allows the learners to take responsibility for their learning and become more independent learners” (Campos, 2007). Developing students into self-motivated learners likely requires shifting the reins of their learning into student hands. In the state of Florida, roughly twenty percent of students are receiving reading intervention. Interventions in Kindergarten focuses on phonological awareness, phonics, and word recognition and are usually taught by a paraprofessional in the classroom, while interventions in third grade focuses on engaging students for longer periods of time with lengthier texts involving more complex skills and are taught by specialized reading intervention teach-

ers (Wanzek Cavanaugh, 2010). The shift from intervention being offered by a paraprofessional to a reading intervention teacher may be because students’ reading scores at the first-grade and second-grade levels consistently grow more rapidly than their peers when they are engaged in high-level thinking about the texts that they read (Peterson Taylor, 2012). Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score.

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.10 with a p-value of .0351 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade one pupils. This implies that cross check approach has validated the oral recitation skills of the grade one learners.

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	38	-5.10	.0351	Significant

This finding is in line with the statement of Yuan (2028) who expressed that some students can’t find the right word when they communicate with others in English with the results that they have the impression they are poor at oral English. On the other hand, because of these

problems, some of the students might give up this opportunity to learn and practice oral English. With the time flying, they become afraid to talk out loud in the class. As a result, the less they speak, the worse their oral English will be. Self-confidence is a trust in one’s self, abilities,

and skills in order to do the tasks and achieve goals. There are lots of factors that influence the speaking activities and one of those is the affective factor in which it relates to the emotional aspect of an individual. It came from the word "affect" which means emotion. Minghe (2013) state that there are two related aspects of affective factor and those are relational factors and individual Confidence: Before and After Oral Recitations 95 Journal of Applied Linguistics and Literature, factors of learners wherein it includes motivation, anxiety, and self-confidence. Among all of these, self-confidence is the most influential factor in the progress of one's speaking skills. In order to have an effective communication, they must develop their communication skills. One of the most effective ways to increase the student's communication skills is oral recitation. In which, oral recitation is an act of saying something aloud in public. It is also an act of student's reply to a question. In Jagobiao National High School, the student's performance on their oral recitation is poor. It is because some students felt uneasy and anx-

ious when they are asked to do oral recitations. They are afraid to speak in front of the class. Their communication skills are not yet fully developed because they cannot communicate very well. They tend to have low self-confidence. But since the teachers keep on giving a task and have it performed orally in front of the class, their self-confidence is boosting and increasing. For every individual, it is very important to be confident as it can help interact and communicate with other people without hesitations.

Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade 5 Students

Table 4 highlights the test of crosscheck approach in validating the oral recitation skills of the grade one learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.291 which signifies large effect. This implies that the application of the crosscheck approach has validated the oral recitation skills of the grade one learners. It also implies that grade one learners have shown development in their oral recitation when validated using the crosscheck approach.

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade One Students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
42	-4.10	0.291	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

This finding is in line with the idea of Leong (2017) who said that in recent years, one of the changes in the English language pedagogy has been the shift from a teacher-centered learning model to a learner-centered learning model. The shift signals a new era in which English-speaking teaching should give room to students to express themselves in speaking the language. Speaking is one of the most important skills to be developed and enhanced as a means of communication (Leong 2017). The modern job market requires good command of English and especially of spoken English. Everybody wish-

ing to get the benefits of modern education, research, science, trade, and technology knows that it is impossible without the working knowledge of English language and good communication skills (Carreira, 2011). A learner may have memorized endless lists of vocabulary but cannot speak fluently. A person who speaks effectively is able to receive and respond to information appropriately. He or she is likely to create a favorable impression of oneself and therefore interact with others effectively and confidently (Gorjian and Asaadinezhad, 2015).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of crosscheck approach on the oral recitation skills of grade one learners.

4.1. Findings—This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Lt. C. Villafuerte Sr., Elementary School, Division of Davao City. The subjects of this study were the 68 grade one pupils – 33 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 35 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

This study revealed that the application of crosscheck approach has validated the oral recitation skills of grade one learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade one learners both the controlled and experimental groups are at the Developing level. The post-test scores of the controlled group are at the Approaching Proficiency level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Proficient level.

4.3. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this

study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers across subject areas and across grade levels should apply crosscheck approach to validate the input they gave and to further determine the skills developed in the learners. Parents and kids can learn strategies to cope with phonological and/or phonemic awareness problems that affect his or her reading. For the parents, you could help your child by reading books with rhymes. Parents can teach their child rhymes, short poems, and songs. For the teacher, make sure the school's reading program and other materials include skill-building in phonemes, especially in kindergarten and first grade (these skills do not come naturally, but must be taught). With the help of parents and teachers, kids can learn strategies to cope with fluency issues that affect his or her reading. Track the words with your finger as a parent or teacher reads a passage aloud. Then you read it. Read your favorite books and poems over and over again. Practice getting smoother and reading with expression. Kids can also overcome vocabulary limitations that affect their reading. Find books to read on your own. The more you read, the newer words you'll see, and the more you'll learn about the words. The school heads should promote the application of crosscheck approach by institutionalizing its application through a memorandum that the said approach should be used in the classroom instruction and to be observed by the school head during classroom observation. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the application of crosscheck approach will be conducted exploring another dimension in the curriculum that will emerge as academic problem to be resolved.

5. References

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